

Chlorination kinetics of copper oxide and cobalt oxide with ammonium chloride

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The kinetics of chlorination of CoO and CuO were studied using thermogravimetric technique. The kinetic results were analyzed by a suitable computer software involving various kinetic laws of gas-solid reaction to find the mechanism and activation energy and have further been substantiated by reduced time plot analysis. The mixed mechanisms of chlorination—contracting geometry and diffusion control—were observed for CuO whereas chlorination of CoO showed single diffusion control. The activation energies of chlorination of copper oxide and cobalt oxide are respectively 6.5 and 95 kJ mol⁻¹.

The chemical processing based on chlorination is becoming a very attractive route because of its selectivity^{1,2}. The mineralogy of ores or minerals can be altered easily by chlorination. So chlorination treatment can be effectively utilized for the recovery of copper and cobalt from complex raw materials.

The chemical reaction for copper and cobalt oxides chlorination with ammonium chloride can be presented as follows

NH₄Cl decomposes² at 350° producing NH₃ and HCl.

HCl so generated reacts with the metal oxides to form the chlorides,

The vapor pressure of copper chloride at 525° is 1 atm³ and that of cobalt chloride 1 atm. at 1000°⁴. So above 525° and 1000°, the copper and cobalt chloride respectively will be transformed into vapor state. The kinetics of high temperature chlorination of copper and cobalt oxides can be measured using thermogravimetric technique⁵. In this technique the temperature-dependent weight-loss of oxides arising out of volatilization of chlorides as function of time are measured. From these measured data kinetic analyses are carried out. The kinetics of metallic copper chlorination was studied by Frommer and Pollany⁶ and the mechanism was found to be diffusion-controlled. Kim and Pickering⁷ studied metallic cobalt chlorination and observed that the transport of gaseous cobalt chloride through the solid particle was important to determine the rate-controlling step.

The present investigation is taken up to understand the chlorination behavior of copper and cobalt oxides with ammonium chloride.

Kinetic data analysis :

The kinetic equation is of the type

$$g(\alpha) = kt \quad (4)$$

where *k* is the reaction rate constant. The functional form of *g*(α) depends on the mechanism. The *g*(α) for different mechanism are shown in Table 1. Using the above reaction mechanisms kinetic data were analyzed statistically by the software based on the following algorithm¹³.

Table 1 Mechanism for different solid state reactions

Symbol	Name	Form of <i>g</i> (α)
D ₁	Parabolic	α^2
D ₂	Valensi-Barrer	$\alpha + (1-\alpha) \ln(1-\alpha)$
D ₃	Ginstling-Brounstein	$1 - 2\alpha/3 - (1-\alpha)^{2/3}$
D ₄	Jander	$[1 - (1-\alpha)^{1/3}]^2$
CG ₁	Contracting geometry (One-dimensional)	α
CG ₂	Contracting geometry (Cylindrical symmetry)	$1 - (1-\alpha)^{1/2}$
CG ₃	Contracting geometry (Spherical symmetry)	$1 - (1-\alpha)^{1/3}$

Step 1. For a particular mechanism and for a given temperature compute *g*(α) as a function of time from α vs *t* plot. Fit the best line, *y* = *mx* by least square method.

Step 2. Check the goodness of fit by

Correlation coefficient (*r*) = cov (*x*,*y*) / 6*x*.6*y*

and normalized error square mean (NESM) =

$$1/n \sum [(y_i - mx_i) / y_i]^2$$

Step 3. Find the slope to give k .

Step 4. Repeat steps 1 to 3 for all temperatures.

Step 5. Fit best straight line of the type, $y = mx + c$ through $\ln k$ vs $1/T$ plot. Goodness of fit is checked by r and NESM. Activation energy is obtained from the slope of straight line. The smaller the NESM and closer the value of r to unity, the better will be the fit.

Results and Discussion

Figs. 1 and 2 show the plots of fraction chlorinated (α) vs time at different temperatures for cobalt oxide and copper oxide system, respectively. The results reveal that as the

Fig. 1. Plots of fraction converted α vs t for CoO.

Fig. 2. Plots of fraction converted α vs t for CuO.

temperature of the chlorination increases, there is a sharp increase in α . For the chlorination of cobalt oxide system, the NESM for α vs time plots for all the mechanisms at 1000, 1025, 1075 and 1100° were scanned from the computer output. The minimum value of the order of 10^{-3} is obtained for the diffusion-control mechanisms compared to 10^{-1} to 10^{-2} for all other mechanisms. We have included data for CG_3 mechanism as typical one for comparison and these are summarized in Table 2. From the value of r and

NESM we see that α vs time of D_1 , D_2 , D_3 and D_4 are very close. However, we find from the Table 2 that for $\ln k$ vs $1/T$ plot, the minimum value for NESM is for mechanism D_3 , while r remains same. Therefore, we predict the mechanism which is operative is D_3 . The spherical pellets used for cobalt oxide chlorination are porous, so the reacting HCl gas will enter into the pellets and will react with cobalt oxide to form cobalt chloride gas, which will diffuse through porous unreacted cobalt oxide. In Ginstling-Brounstein type of mechanism, the product gas diffuses out through porous layer. So Ginstling-Brounstein mechanism is consistent with physical reasoning. The activation energy for the reaction is $\sim 95 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Table 2. Statistical data analysis of cobalt oxide chlorination

Mechanism	Temp. °C	Corr. coeff. (r)	NESM $\times 10^{-3}$ α vs t	Activation energy kJ mol^{-1}	Corr. coeff. (r) $\ln k$ vs $1/T$	NESM $\times 10^{-3}$ $\ln k$ vs $1/T$
D_1	1000	0.995	6.53	90.52	0.989	1.18
	1025	0.996	3.20			
	1075	0.997	2.64			
	1100	0.997	2.76			
D_2	1000	0.995	4.89	94.05	0.989	1.15
	1025	0.996	3.33			
	1075	0.997	4.53			
	1100	0.997	1.88			
D_3	1000	0.995	4.43	95.28	0.989	0.926
	1025	0.996	3.58			
	1075	0.997	5.53			
	1100	0.997	1.88			
D_4	1000	0.995	3.70	97.74	0.989	0.989
	1025	0.996	4.42			
	1075	0.997	8.00			
	1100	0.997	2.40			
CG_3	1000	0.995	199.0	3.88	0.988	0.410
	1025	0.996	197.0			
	1075	0.997	196.0			
	1100	0.997	196.0			

Table 3 presents the data for CuO chlorination in the same way as outlined for CoO system. The results reveal that the predicted mechanism is CG_3 . In Table 3 we have incorporated the data of mechanisms CG and D_3 for comparison. The activation energy is about 6.5 kJ mol^{-1} . For further confirmation of mechanisms of the chlorination of cobalt oxide and copper oxide based on statistical analysis of kinetic data, the reduce time plot⁵ analysis was carried out as outlined below :

$$g(\alpha) = kt \quad (4)$$

$$\text{for } \alpha = 0.15,$$

$$g(0.15) = kt_{0.15} \quad (5)$$

where, $t_{0.15}$ is the time required for 15% conversion. Dividing (4) by (5), we get

$$g(\alpha)/g(0.15) = t/t_{0.15} = \theta \quad (6)$$

where, θ is the reduced time. So from the eqn. (6) we see that α vs θ plot is independent of k , the reaction rate constant, which is the temperature dependent term in kinetics. Therefore, for the single mechanism operative over the entire ranges of temperature, the computed α vs θ plot from experimental data, will coincide with theoretically computed α vs θ plot for the same mechanism. Hence, by com-

Fig. 3. Plots of fraction converted vs reduced time for CoO

paring the matching of the computed α vs θ plot from the experimental data with those of the theoretically computed α vs θ plot for all the mechanisms, we can find out which

Fig. 4. Plots of fraction converted vs reduced time for CuO

mechanism is operative. Fig. 3 shows the theoretical reduced time plots for the mechanism of diffusion and contracting geometry type along with the α vs θ plot computed from the experimental data of chlorination of cobalt oxide. Similarly, Fig. 4 shows the reduced time plot of copper oxide chlorination. By comparing the experimental data with theoretical one, we conclude that the mechanism is of contracting geometry type as was predicted by the statistical analysis for CuO chlorination. However, for higher fraction of transformation, the reaction mechanism tends to change towards the diffusion type of mechanism (D_3). Initially the reaction mechanism is CG_3 but as the reaction proceeds there is a chance that some porous unreacted copper oxide remains at the outer layer, and at the later stage, the gaseous copper chloride will diffuse out through this unreacted layer causing D_3 mechanism to be operative. From the Fig. 3 we see that the experimental one matches closely to the theoretically computed α vs θ plot for D_3 which is predicted by statistical analysis.

Table 3 Statistical data analysis of copper oxide chlorination

Mechanism	Temp °C	Corr coeff (r)	NESM α vs t	Activation energy kJ/mol ⁻¹	Corr coeff (r)	NESM $\ln k$ vs $1/T$
CG1	625	0.993	1.55×10^{-1}	105.50	0.959	0.1458×10^{-3}
	650	0.971	1.60×10^{-2}			
	675	0.949	3.06×10^{-2}			
	700	0.987	3.59×10^{-2}			
CG2	625	0.993	1.49×10^{-1}	109.40	0.960	0.1323×10^{-3}
	650	0.973	1.34×10^{-2}			
	675	0.957	2.74×10^{-2}			
	700	0.988	3.00×10^{-2}			
CG3	625	0.994	1.84×10^{-1}	6.48	0.978	0.41×10^{-6}
	650	0.971	1.83×10^{-1}			
	675	0.949	1.83×10^{-1}			
	700	0.986	1.78×10^{-1}			
D3	625	0.946	46.20	207.74	0.964	0.24×10^{-3}
	650	0.989	1.33			
	675	0.986	1.19			
	700	0.979	3.50×10^{-1}			

Conclusions :

(i) Temperature has drastic influence on the rate of chlorination of both copper and cobalt oxides. (ii) Copper oxide shows three-dimensional contracting geometry with tendency towards Ginstling-Brounsthein diffusion-controlled mechanism at the higher fraction of conversion. (iii) Cobalt oxide shows Ginstling-Brounsthein diffusion-controlled mechanism over the entire range of conversion; the activation energy for the reaction is 95 kJ mol^{-1} .

Experimental

The cupric oxide and cobalt oxide pellets were prepared from A.R. grade powder (E. Merck) with adequate amount of moisture. The cupric oxide pellets were then dried,

preheated and fired at 800° for 1 h and the cobalt oxide pellets fired at 1000° for 1 h. The diameter of cupric oxide pellets was maintained 12 ± 1 mm and that for cobalt oxide 9 ± 1 mm with porosity around 60%. The pellet was suspended from a thermogravimetric electronic balance attached to the furnace and necessary chlorination atmosphere was maintained by feeding ammonium chloride salts from the bottom. The cupric oxide and cobalt oxide chlorination was studied at 625, 700 and 1000–1100°. Nitrogen gas was flushed at a rate of 0.4×10^{-4} m³. The P_{HCl} in the reactor was maintained around 0.2 atm. The chlorination of oxides progressed as per reactions (2) and (3) at a given temperature. The fraction of oxides (α) converted as a function of time was computed from the time-dependent weight-loss of the each pellet.

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